

Revolutionizing UAV-Enabled Communications via Omnidirectional Multi-Rotor Aerial Vehicles

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Abstract—A new class of Multi-Rotor Aerial Vehicles (MRAVs), known as omnidirectional MRAVs (o-MRAVs), has attracted significant interest in the robotics community. These MRAVs have the unique capability of independently controlling their 3D position and 3D orientation. In the context of aerial communication networks, this translates into the ability to control the position and orientation of the antenna mounted on the MRAV without any additional devices tasked for antenna orientation. This additional Degrees of Freedom (DoF) adds a new dimension to aerial communication systems, creating various research opportunities in communications-aware trajectory planning and positioning. This paper presents this new class of MRAVs and discusses use cases in areas such as physical layer security and optical communications. Furthermore, the benefits of these MRAVs are illustrated with realistic simulation scenarios. Finally, we discuss new research problems and opportunities that this advanced robotics technology brings.

Index Terms—Multi-Rotor Aerial Vehicles, Communication-Aware Robotics, Pose Optimization, Antenna Orientation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, the integration of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) into wireless networks has garnered significant attention from both academic and industrial research communities [1]. UAVs have been studied in wireless communications for two main reasons. First, their agility and swift deployment allow UAVs to be quickly positioned to address changing demands and optimize network performance [1], [2]. Second, their performance in achieving Line-of-Sight (LoS) significantly improves the reliability of communication links and expands the coverage area [3], [4]. Consequently, UAVs have been considered for a wide range of applications. Specifically, they have been identified as agile solutions to replace damaged base stations in post-disaster recovery scenarios. Additionally, they have been considered as efficient relays for collecting data from remote Internet of Thing (IoT) devices. Furthermore, UAVs have been explored as aerial base stations to enhance network capacity in densely populated areas and underserved regions [1], [3].

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In this context, a considerable portion of the existing literature focuses on Multi-Rotor Aerial Vehicles (MRAVs), specifically on a single design: the under-actuated MRAV (u-MRAV). In this design, UAVs are characterized by having fewer actuation inputs – such as thrust, pitch and roll angles, and yaw rate – than Degrees of Freedom (DoF) (their 3D position and their 3D orientation). This implies that the 3D orientation of u-MRAVs is dependent on their translational velocity. In other words, independently controlling the 3D position and 3D orientation of u-MRAVs is not feasible as they are unable to control their thrust and torque in all three axes [5].

Despite the aforementioned limitation, u-MRAVs continue to be a popular subject of research due to their reduced weight, cost, and mechanical simplicity. However, they present multiple challenges. The underactuation of u-MRAVs causes them to tilt during motion or when compensating for external forces (e.g., wind), introducing additional complications in *communication-aware* trajectory planning [6]. This is because the movement and associated tilt can alter the orientation of the onboard antenna, thereby affecting the communication channel [3]. This problem will be exacerbated when terahertz (THz) and mmWave communication technologies, intended for use in 6G, are mounted on the UAVs due to the high directivity of the antennas. Nevertheless, most scientific papers that address communication-aware trajectory planning problems fail to consider this effect, which can significantly impact system performance depending on the trajectory of the u-MRAV. In these papers, the authors implicitly and incorrectly assume that if the u-MRAV moves, its 3D orientation remains constant as if it were hovering or not effected by external forces. This assumption is only valid at low velocities and when the pitch and roll orientation angles are below 10 degrees [5], which limits their applicability in real-world scenarios.

Recently, the robotics community has introduced new designs for MRAVs known as fully actuated MRAVs (f-MRAVs) and omnidirectional MRAVs (o-MRAVs) [5]. These MRAVs are designed with a total thrust vector that can be varied in all directions independently from the torque, and with more than one input combination. This means there are more actuation inputs than DoF, allowing for partial (f-MRAVs) or total (o-MRAVs) independent control over each movement axis. This capability significantly increases the range of maneuvers MRAVs can perform and ensures a meticulous control of their orientation. From a communication perspective, this feature is crucial for tasks requiring precise antenna positioning, as it ensures that the antenna's orientation remains controlled throughout the UAV's mission when fixed on the

Figure 1: Illustration of u-MRAV and o-MRAV configurations, along with the global and untilted reference frames [8]. Arcs represent the rotation direction of servos used for varying the thrust vector.

MRAV frame. Figure 1 presents an illustrative example of both an u-MRAV and an o-MRAV.

While the integration of additional control inputs in o-MRAVs, compared to f-MRAVs, presents challenges such as managing more optimization parameters and dealing with increased costs and design complexities (additional moving parts), these vehicles offer significant advantages in wireless networks. Previous work by the authors [7] was the first to introduce o-MRAVs in the domain of communications, highlighting their specific advantages. This new class of MRAVs adds a new dimension to the communication-aware trajectory planning and positioning problems by allowing the independent optimization of both the 3D orientation and 3D position of the antenna. Therefore, this paper explores how this new capability can be leveraged to enhance communication systems in various settings.

II. O-MRAVS: DESIGN, MODELING AND CONTROL

When discussing the design of o-MRAVs, it is important to note that several actuation strategies have been proposed in the literature. According to [5], [8], the design of o-MRAVs can be divided into three classes: (i) *bi-directional* propellers, which generate thrust in both directions by inverting their rotation, (ii) *uni-directional* propellers, which generate thrust in only one direction, either rotating clockwise or counterclockwise, and (iii) *actively tilted* propellers, where each propeller tilts individually around its radial axis using servo motors. Among the three designs, the third one is the most flexible, allowing adjustments in propeller orientation and rotation direction to enhance platform efficiency and payload capacity. These advantages come with a more complicated mechanical design and control strategy, which must optimize the propeller spinning rate, orientation, and direction (clockwise or counterclockwise).

For this study, an actively titled o-MRAV with eight bi-directional propellers is considered. These propellers are attached to the vertices of a cube centered at the vehicle's Center of Mass (CoM), as discussed in [8] and depicted in Figure 1. Each propeller tilts around a different axis by the same angle, referred to as the *tilting angle*. This configuration allows the total thrust vector to point in all three orthogonal axis directions.

Fundamental to the modeling of an o-MRAV platform is the definition of reference frames and key parameters which include the mass of the o-MRAV, its inertia, position, global velocity, attitude unit quaternion, and body angular velocity. The modeling defines two reference frames: the untilted frame, centered at the MRAV's CoM with axes aligned to the edges of a cube, and the global reference frame, as shown in Figure 1.

The dynamics of the o-MRAV are modeled as a six DoF floating rigid body using the Newton-Euler formalism. In this model, the state of the system includes position, orientation, velocity, and angular velocity, while the control inputs are the squared rotor speeds of the eight bi-directional propellers, their spinning direction, and the tilt angles of the propellers. The rotors generate forces and torques at the o-MRAV's CoM. The total force is a combination of the thrusts generated by all rotors, while the total torque arises from the combined momenta produced by these rotors. These forces and torques depend on constant parameters related to the propeller's shape, the positions of the rotors in the untilted frame, and the unit vectors parallel to the rotor rotation axes. Further details are available in [5], [8].

A. Comparative evaluation of o-MRAVs capabilities

The capabilities of o-MRAVs are evaluated in comparison to their under-actuated (u-MRAVs) and fully actuated (f-MRAVs) counterparts. As outlined in [5], [8], these abilities are significantly influenced by the mechanical design of the platforms. The mechanical design of f-MRAVs limits their ability to control position and orientation independently in most directions. In contrast, o-MRAVs can achieve full independent control over their 3D position and 3D orientation, enabling more complex and precise maneuvers. This enhanced capability is primarily due to the o-MRAV's ability to control the spinning direction and speed of the rotors along with the tilting angles (see Figure 1). In comparison, f-MRAVs have fixed tilting angles and, in most cases, fixed spinning directions, with only the motors' speed being variable. For a thorough comparison, three representative features are considered: hovering ability, trajectory tracking ability, and robustness to rotor failures.

Hovering ability. The *ability to hover* refers to the capability of MRAVs to remain stationary at a desired position. This is particularly relevant for applications where UAVs act as aerial Base Stations (BSs) or as communication relays [3], representing a major advantage of multi-rotors over fixed-wing UAVs. According to [5], [8], for MRAVs, hovering can be classified into static and dynamic hovering. *Static hovering* is the platform's ability to stabilize its position and orientation with zero linear and angular velocity, allowing for heading changes. *Dynamic hovering*, on the other hand, involves maintaining a bounded position error while varying linear and angular velocities, achieved through continuous movements around a point.

u-MRAVs can only achieve static hovering, while f-MRAVs and o-MRAVs can perform both static and dynamic hovering. Additionally, unlike f-MRAVs, o-MRAVs can maintain a constant position while varying its orientation in space. This constitutes the main advantage of o-MRAVs compared

Table I: Comparison of included system abilities, based on the MRV design: “included” (✓), “partially included” (*), and “not included” (✗)

MRV designs	System Abilities				
	Static Hovering	Dynamic Hovering	Position Tracking	Orientation Tracking	Failure Robustness
u-MRAV	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
f-MRAV	✓	*	✓	*	*
o-MRAV	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

to u-MRAV and f-MRAV designs. Thus, for o-MRAVs with a rigidly attached antenna to their CoM, this capability allows the antenna to be directed towards a specific target without changing the vehicle’s position.

Trajectory tracking ability. The ability to follow a trajectory is fundamental for many applications. Like the hovering ability, trajectory tracking ability can be divided based on the type (position and orientation tracking) and the number of DoF the MRV can track independently.

For u-MRAVs, only three-dimensional position and one-dimensional attitude orientation tracking are possible. This means it is not possible to control the pitch and roll angles, as they are coupled with the vehicle’s position movements. Conversely, f-MRAVs can achieve three-dimensional position and two-dimensional attitude tracking [5]. However, these platforms are still unable to exploit their full DoF, limiting their applications despite some advantages over u-MRAV. Only o-MRAVs can achieve three-dimensional position and three-dimensional attitude tracking. These platforms are most suitable for counteracting windy and turbulent conditions [9], thus reducing the jittering effects often encountered with u-MRAVs [10].

Rotor failure robustness. f-MRAVs and o-MRAVs might be mistakenly thought to be more robust to rotor failures compared to u-MRAVs due to their higher number of rotors¹. However, their actual robustness is primarily attributed to their static and dynamic hovering capabilities. *Rotor failure* is defined as a scenario where a propeller becomes unusable and cannot produce any thrust. In the case of u-MRAV, the failure of a propeller results in the platform’s inability to control its attitude, and hence to safely land, unless sophisticated algorithms and additional sensors are employed. In contrast, f-MRAVs and o-MRAV can maintain stable flight even after losing one or more propellers [11]. Specifically, o-MRAVs, with their ability to reorient propellers and change spinning direction, are most flexible and robust platforms compared to f-MRAVs.

Table I presents a comparison of system abilities associated with different MRV designs. The table categorizes the abilities as “included” (✓), “partially included” (*), and “not included” (✗) for each design, providing a clear overview of the capabilities and limitations of u-MRAV, f-MRAV, and o-MRAV platforms.

¹Typically, u-MRAVs have four to eight rotors, often with double opposed propellers to increase lift [5].

B. Challenges and open problems

The development and deployment of o-MRAVs present several challenges and open problems that must be addressed to fully harness their potential. This section outlines the primary obstacles in the areas of control system complexity, energy consumption, and design costs, compared to u-MRAVs and f-MRAVs counterparts, providing insights into the current state of research and the ongoing efforts to overcome these issues.

Control system complexity. The control systems of o-MRAVs are inherently more complex due to their ability to independently control both position and orientation. This capability adds a new layer of complexity to the three-dimensional positioning and trajectory planning of the vehicles. Specifically, optimizing the orientation of antennas on o-MRAVs involves handling nonlinear, non-convex, and non-smooth optimization problems. These challenges make it difficult to find optimal solutions within a reasonable time frame, as solvers can easily become trapped in local optima. Consequently, sophisticated algorithms are required to optimize both the positioning and orientation of o-MRAVs, ensuring their efficient deployment [1], [3], [6].

Energy consumption. A significant challenge in the development and use of o-MRAVs is balancing performance and efficiency. For o-MRAVs, the propellers must generate sufficient lift so that total thrust vector can overcome gravity, along with an additional margin to support dynamic maneuvers. This performance requirement is at odds with the goal of achieving high efficiency and extended flight times. Efficiency is compromised in systems where thrust forces oppose each other or when additional weight is introduced for actuation mechanisms. To address this challenge, ongoing research is focused on finding optimal design strategies that efficiently manage the lift produced by the propellers by adjusting the tilting angles and the spinning direction [8].

Costs and design complexity. Despite their advantages, o-MRAVs also have drawbacks, such as additional actuation mass, increased design complexity, and the presence of singularity cases not encountered in u-MRAVs [5]. Therefore, morphology design is crucial to ensure that the resulting platform meets performance requirements. This necessitates the use of proper optimization tools² capable of performing parametric optimization of the tilting angles and the propeller positions relative to the MRV’s CoM. The goal is to maximize the force and torque envelope and their maximum values in each axis direction. As a result, compared to their more commonly used u-MRAV counterparts, many of o-MRAV platforms are designed and developed within laboratory environments, increasing their costs [12].

III. USE CASES

The primary advantage of o-MRAVs is their ability to independently control both orientation and position. From a communication perspective, this capability means that, when the antenna is fixed to the o-MRAVs frame, both its 3D

²https://github.com/ethz-asl/tiltrotor_morphology_optimization

position and 3D orientation can be precisely managed. This unlocks new and interesting opportunities in the field. In this section, we describe some potential use cases in wireless communication networks where the unique characteristics of o-MRAVs can lead to significant enhancements and introduce innovative approaches to traditional challenges. Figure 2 summarizes the studied use cases.

A. Physical layer security

A traditional challenge in physical layer security is maximizing the secrecy rate during communication between two legitimate nodes in the presence of an eavesdropper. Conventional strategies often employ multi-antenna arrays to direct the radiation pattern's null towards the eavesdropper while enhancing the antenna gain experienced by the legitimate receiver.

However, if the legitimate transmitter is an o-MRAV, similar results can be achieved using a single antenna. This is accomplished by manipulating the 3D orientation of the o-MRAV, allowing the null of the o-MRAV antenna's radiation pattern to be directed towards the eavesdropper while maintaining communication with the legitimate node.

In a related scenario, if a legitimate network faces an attack by a malicious jammer, and the legitimate receivers are o-MRAVs with single antennas, they can reorient themselves to direct their antenna radiation pattern's null towards the jammer. This strategic repositioning can mitigate and neutralize the jamming attack [7].

B. Capacity enhancement in dense areas

The goal of network densification is to enhance network performance and coverage by deploying a large number of small cells within a target area. MRAVs have been considered as rapidly deployable aerial BSs to improve network quality of service. However, network densification can result in high interference and increased coordination costs, leading to additional optimization and planning challenges.

To address this challenge, o-MRAVs can mechanically control the antenna's orientation and direct the signal to reduce interference. By equipping an o-MRAV with a highly directional antenna and combining it with an effective orientation and position controller, communication can be provided in a highly focused and dynamic manner. This approach allows connectivity to be delivered to specific users, thereby improving the spatial sharing of the electromagnetic spectrum and minimizing interference [1].

C. Localization of RF sources

Localization of Radio Frequency (RF) sources is a critical task in various applications, such as search and rescue operations, and identifying the position of malicious jammers. MRAVs equipped with directional antennas and sometimes additional mechanical systems for antenna rotation are commonly used for this task. Typically, MRAVs vary their yaw angle to orient the antenna in different directions and collect data to localize the target. While effective, this method has limitations in terms of flexibility and speed.

In contrast, o-MRAVs offer significant advantages in RF source localization. These advanced MRAVs can independently control the roll and pitch angles, in addition to the yaw angle. This enhanced maneuverability allows for the design of more efficient trajectories and enable faster and more accurate localization of RF sources even without a special system for antenna positioning. By leveraging their full range of motion, o-MRAVs achieve superior performance in tasks requiring precise and rapid localization of RF signals.

D. Aerial Free-Space Optical communications

Free-Space Optical (FSO) communications is one of the most promising applications for o-MRAVs. Achieving successful FSO communication requires establishing direct links between the transmitter and receiver, particularly when using flying robots. This leads to the alignment problem [13]. The transmitting MRAVs must precisely direct its laser beam to the center of the optical receiver on the other MRAVs, while the receiving MRAVs must align its lens and photodiode with the incoming laser beam. Maintaining a precise alignment is crucial for effective FSO communication, as even slight deviations can lead to signal loss or degradation.

u-MRAVs often struggle with this alignment due to their limited ability to control orientation independently of their position. In contrast, o-MRAVs offer a substantial advantage in this regard. Their flexible orientation capabilities allow for precise positioning and alignment of the laser beam and optical receiver.

Additionally, u-MRAVs are more prone to jittering, which further complicates the alignment problem. Using o-MRAVs mitigates the impact of jittering, as these MRAVs are less sensitive to such disturbances.

E. THz and mmWave communications

Some of the key technologies expected to be deployed in 6G networks include THz communications and mmWave communications. The extremely high frequencies of these systems will provide very large bandwidths but will also introduce significant absorption losses. To compensate for these losses, 6G systems will utilize high-gain antennas which are highly directional.

When establishing aerial links between MRAVs using these technologies, the same alignment problem described for aerial FSO communications will arise (see Section III-D). High directivity antennas require precise alignment to maintain a strong communication link. Consequently, o-MRAVs will exhibit significant advantages when establishing aerial RF links using these technologies. Their ability to independently control position and orientation will simplify the alignment process, enhance link stability, and improve the overall reliability of 6G communications involving MRAVs.

IV. SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS: O-MRAVs FOR JAMMING AND EAVESDROPPING MITIGATION

In the area of physical layer security, o-MRAVs offer significant advantages over u-MRAVs. This section explores

Figure 2: o-MRAV use cases.

two scenarios where the deployment of o-MRAVs proves to be highly efficient. The first scenario involves an o-MRAV communicating with a legitimate node in the presence of a jammer. We demonstrate how the o-MRAV can direct its antenna to enhance communication efficiency [7]. In the second scenario, we consider the presence of eavesdroppers attempting to intercept the communication. A friendly jammer is employed to disrupt the eavesdropping and protect the communication [14].

Figure 3: (a) An o-MRAV communicating with a legitimate user in the presence of a jammer, (b) a friendly jammer disrupting eavesdroppers.

A. Enhancing security against jamming with o-MRAVs

We consider a legitimate network composed of two ground nodes and one o-MRAV, as depicted in Figure 3(a) and described in [7]. The o-MRAV receives data streams from the ground nodes while a malicious ground node emits a jamming signal towards the o-MRAV to disrupt communications. The objective is to optimize the 3D position and 3D orientation of the o-MRAV to maximize the minimum Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) for both ground users.

To achieve this, we test four different strategies: (i) *Optimum Pose*, numerically optimizing the position and orientation of

the o-MRAV; (ii) *Maximum Gain*, orienting the o-MRAV so that the main lobe of its antenna radiation pattern points towards the ground users, then numerically optimizing its position; (iii) *Zero Interference*, orienting the o-MRAV so that the null of its antenna radiation pattern points towards the jammer, then numerically optimizing its position; (iv) *Vertical Orientation*, optimizing the position of an u-MRAV with a single vertically oriented antenna.

From Figure 4, several observations can be made. When the jamming signal is weak, the *Maximum Gain* solution matches the optimal one. As the jamming signal becomes stronger, the *Zero Interference* solution becomes optimal. Therefore, sub-optimal solutions yield optimal poses under extreme jamming conditions.

Another observation is the saturation of all solutions when the strength of the jamming signal increases. The performance of the *Zero Interference* solution remains constant because it consistently nullifies the jamming signal. The optimal solution approaches the *Zero Interference* solution, eventually nullifying the jamming signal. The *Maximum Gain* solution continues to maximize its antenna gain for the legitimate nodes but starts adjusting its position so that the null of its antenna points towards the jammer. The *Vertical Orientation* solution moves towards the jammer until the MRAV positions itself directly above the jammer, effectively pointing its null towards it and completely neutralizing the jamming. These results demonstrate the advantages of optimizing the position and orientation of the o-MRAV to establish robust communication in the presence of jamming attacks.

Comparing the optimal performance of the o-MRAV (blue plot in Figure 4) to the u-MRAV (magenta plot in Figure 4), we observe significant performance differences, especially under strong jamming conditions. It is worth noting that the frame of the MRAV has the potential to modify the radiation pattern of the antenna [15].

Figure 4: Minimum SINR for different jamming powers.

B. Friendly jammer o-MRAV against eavesdroppers

In this second scenario, we consider a downlink communication where an o-MRAV communicates with a legitimate ground node in the presence of two eavesdroppers, as depicted in Figure 3(b) and described in [14]. To protect the legitimate communication, a second o-MRAV is deployed with the task of jamming the eavesdroppers. The goal is to optimize the position and orientation of both o-MRAVs and their transmission power to maximize the secrecy rate of the legitimate user.

The optimization strategy is as follows: for the jamming o-MRAV, we set its orientation so that the null of its radiation pattern always points towards the legitimate user. This allows the jamming o-MRAV to radiate as much as possible without degrading the communications of the legitimate user. This constraint uniquely determines the orientation of the jamming o-MRAV at each position. For the communicating o-MRAV, we fix its orientation so that the maximum of its antenna radiation pattern always points to the legitimate user, while maximizing the horizontal distance between the maximum antenna gain projection line and the eavesdroppers. This also uniquely determines the orientation of the o-MRAV for a given location. Finally, we optimize the 3D positions of both o-MRAVs and their transmission powers.

We compare this approach with two different strategies used as benchmarks:

- *Interior-point method*: Solves the optimization problem with respect to all variables, including the orientations, positions, and powers of the MRAVs, using the interior-point method.
- *Conventional MRAV*: Assumes u-MRAVs with fixed orientation and employs the interior-point method to optimize the MRAVs positions and transmit powers.

Figure 5 illustrates the dependency of the secrecy rate on the maximum power in case of our proposed approach, compared to the two benchmarks. The figure highlights a substantial performance advantage of the proposed approach, showing an increase of gain compared to the interior-point method. This significant improvement is attributed to the non-convex nature of the secrecy rate function, which can cause the interior-point method to become stuck in a local optimum, deviating significantly from the optimal performance. Additionally, the

Figure 5: Secrecy rate versus maximum power for 2 eavesdroppers.

figure shows that the conventional u-MRAV performs the worst due to its inability to optimize antenna orientation, resulting in very poor performance.

V. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

The introduction of o-MRAVs into communication networks offers the potential to optimize both the 3D position and 3D orientation of onboard antennas. This innovation raises several key questions for future research, as described next.

Optimal 3D Orientation and Positioning: A significant area of investigation involves determining the best position and antenna orientation for o-MRAVs to optimize communication performance across various use cases. This includes analyzing different scenarios to understand how precise positioning and orientation can maximize Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), minimize interference, and ensure reliable connectivity.

Energy Consumption: o-MRAVs are designed with thrust forces that often oppose each other, and additional weight is introduced for the actuation mechanisms (see Section II-B). This design increases energy consumption and affects mission endurance. To ensure that these vehicles gain popularity and use in the communication field, significant research is needed to minimize energy consumption while maximizing communication performance.

Trajectory Planning: Another crucial aspect involves planning the trajectory of o-MRAVs to optimize their movements for efficient communication and navigation. This task requires careful consideration of the dynamical model of o-MRAVs, taking into account the forces and torques applied to the CoM by the rotors, and the orientation of the antenna to enhance the transmission rate. The goal is to ensure that these vehicles can navigate complex environments while maintaining optimal positions for communication.

2D and 3D beamforming. It is essential to investigate the performance of o-MRAV-assisted networks when equipped with antenna arrays. These arrays facilitate beamforming techniques, enabling precise control over beam direction. Integrating o-MRAVs with 2D and 3D beamforming has the potential to substantially enhance network performance and support higher data rates.

These areas of research are critical for unlocking the full potential of o-MRAVs to enhance the performance of communication systems.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented omnidirectional MRAVs and detailed their ability to independently control 3D position and orientation. We compared these advanced MRAVs to u-MRAV and f-MRAV counterparts, highlighting their superior hovering ability, trajectory tracking, and rotor failure robustness. We demonstrated how o-MRAVs can enhance network performance in use cases such as physical layer security, localization, and network capacity. Simulation results showed their effectiveness in mitigating jamming and eavesdropping attacks, emphasizing their potential in secure communications. Future research should focus on optimizing 3D orientation and positioning, minimizing energy consumption, planning efficient trajectories, and integrating advanced beamforming techniques. Our findings indicate that o-MRAVs can offer significant improvements over traditional MRAV designs, making them a promising technology for future communication networks.

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VII. BIOGRAPHIES

DANIEL BONILLA LICEA earned his Ph.D. in 2016 from the University of Leeds, U.K. Currently, he is an assistant professor at Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P) University, Morocco, and an associated researcher at the Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU-P). His research focuses on signal processing and communications-aware robotics. His main research interest is on communications-aware robotics.

HAJAR ELHAMMOUTI joined UM6P University as an assistant professor in 2021. She earned her Ph.D. from the National Institute of Posts and Telecommunications, Rabat, Morocco, in 2017. She served as a postdoctoral fellow at King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Saudi Arabia, from 2018 to 2020, and at the International University of Rabat from 2017 to 2018. Her research focuses on modeling and optimizing aerial and spatial communication systems.

GIUSEPPE SILANO is a tenured researcher at Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico and an associated researcher at CTU-P. He earned his Ph.D. in 2020 from the University of Sannio, Italy. From 2020 to 2022, he was a postdoctoral researcher at CTU-P. He was a visiting researcher at LAAS-CNRS in 2020 and at the University of Twente in 2022. His research interests include UAV motion planning, model predictive control, formal methods for robotics, communication-aware robotics, and human-robot collaboration. He has authored over 25 peer-reviewed publications. Since 2022, he has been an Associate Editor for several international conferences.

MOUNIR GHOGHO has received the PhD degree in 1997 from the National Polytechnic Institute of Toulouse, France. He was an EPSRC Research Fellow with the University of Strathclyde, U.K., from 1997 to 2001. In 2002, he joined the University of Leeds, U.K., where he was promoted to full Professor in 2008. While still affiliated with the University of Leeds, in 2010 he joined the International University of Rabat where he is currently Dean of the College of Doctoral Studies and Director of TICLab. He is a Fellow of IEEE, a recipient of the 2013 IBM Faculty Award, and a recipient of the 2000 U.K. Royal Academy of Engineering Research Fellowship. His research interests are in Machine Learning, Signal Processing and Wireless Communication. He has served as Associate Editor of many esteemed journals and has been a member of several IEEE technical committees.

MARTIN SASKA holds an M.Sc. from Czech Technical University, Czechia, in 2005 and a Ph.D. from the University of Wuerzburg, Germany, in 2009. He was a Visiting Scholar at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign in 2008 and the University of Pennsylvania in 2012, 2014, and 2016. Since 2009, he has been with the Czech Technical University, Czechia, first as a research fellow and then as an associate professor, leading the Multi-Robot Systems Lab and co-founding the Center for Robotics and Autonomous Systems. He has authored/coauthored more than 90 peer-reviewed conference papers and 60 journal publications.